

Defects Experienced in the Production
of Advanced Composite Outer Wings for
the A-7D Attack Aircraft

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Introduction

Vought Corporation, in a program sponsored by the U.S. Air Force Materials Laboratory*, has built twelve advanced composite outer wings for the A-7D. The A-7D is a subsonic attack aircraft used by Tactical Air Command. Four of the outer wings were used for ground and flight tests to certify it for operational usage by service personnel. The remaining eight wings were installed on aircraft at two Air Force bases located within the United States. The composite wing is shown installed on an A-7 aircraft in Figure 1.

The outer wings were manufactured in a standard production environment. Production personnel were used and the rate of production (1 wing every 9 days) duplicated the metal outer wing panel rate. A total of 2016 parts were fabricated for the eight outer wings. This paper discusses the types of defects that occurred during manufacture of these operational wings.

At the present time, there are several industry and government sponsored programs investigating the effect of defects [1-5]. This composite outer wing structure was produced at a time when the data base available for assessing effects of defects was quite limited. When this data base was not sufficient for a rational disposition it was supplemented by additional tests. A summary of all defects encountered and frequency of occurrence is discussed. Rejection rate of parts and number of scrapped parts is also presented.

Structural Description

Left-hand outer wing panels of the A-7D aircraft were built of composite material. The primary structural box was constructed of hybrid boron-graphite/epoxy covers and graphite/epoxy substructure (spars, ribs) as shown in Figure 2. The existing A-7D metal leading edge spar, fixed trailing edge, and wingfold rib were retained. The standard metal leading edge flap and aileron are also used. The composite main box area is 2.23 square meters (24 square feet). The outer wing has a span of 2.44 meters (96 inches) and a chord at the wingfold joint of 2.92 meters (115 inches). Airfoil thickness (t/c) is seven percent.

* Air Force Contract F33615-73-C-5066; Mr. Charles Tanis was Program Monitor.

FIGURE 1 A-7D COWP INSTALLED ON AIRCRAFT

FIGURE 2 STRUCTURAL DESCRIPTION

Upper and lower wing covers are honeycomb sandwich panels with graphite-boron/epoxy hybrid faces and aluminum core. Materials are Narmco 5208/T300 graphite prepreg and Avco 5505 boron prepreg. Boron/epoxy material is oriented in the 0° (spanwise) direction. Graphite/epoxy material is used in the +45° and 90° directions. In a strip along the mid spar fasteners the 0° B/Ep is replaced with 0° G/Ep. Along the front and rear spars the 0° B/Ep is replaced with +45° G/Ep.

The front, mid, and rear spars are graphite/epoxy. The webs are sandwich construction with aluminum honeycomb core. Flanges are solid graphite/epoxy laminate approximately 0.5 cm (0.2 in.) thick. All of the seventeen rib sections are graphite/epoxy. Some of the ribs are solid laminate construction and some are honeycomb sandwich construction. Narmco 5209/T300 graphite prepreg material is used for all of the substructure.

Manufacturing Procedure

The outer wing panel design is based on the use of 180°C (350°F) cure materials for the wing covers and 130°C (260°F) cure materials for the substructure.

Covers

Manufacture of the covers (honeycomb sandwich panels) was performed in the following sequence. Inner face was layed up and autoclave cured on a molding tool. The aluminum honeycomb core was positioned on the cured inner face. An adhesive film was applied to the exposed core surface and the assembly cured in an autoclave. This stabilized the core. Doublers and core inserts which had been layed up and pre-bled were then placed on the core. Cured inner face, honeycomb core sub-assembly, doublers, inserts and outer face were then assembled with appropriate adhesives and autoclave cocured.

Spars

Each spar was totally cocured in steel tools. The spars were tooled to the outside surface to provide an accurate and smooth surface for bonding to the covers.

Ribs

The manufacturing approach for the composite ribs was established by the subcontractor, Composite Horizons Industries. There are 17 separate ribs required for each ship set. A unique process of producing modular multi-ply sheets of material was developed by the subcontractor. Solid graphite ribs consisting of webs and separate flanges were cured on aluminum tools. Honeycomb core and graphite sandwich ribs were fabricated in two stages. The graphite faces and flanges were precured and then bonded to the honeycomb core in a separate operation.

Assembly

The approach used for assembly consisted of four primary phases. In the first phase, pre-fit and assembly operations of the torque box components was performed followed by drilling of all attach holes. The second phase included application of adhesive to the bond interfaces, assembly of the torque box structure (less upper cover), and installation of associated fasteners. The third phase completed the assembly including installation of the upper cover and trailing edge assembly. The remaining systems installations and checkout, assembly of doors and wing tip fairing was completed in phase four. This final phase also included installation and rigging of the leading edge flap and aileron and painting.

Quality Control Procedures

Receiving inspections were conducted on all purchased materials. All aspects of detail processing were controlled by surveillance inspection. Autoclave cure cycles were controlled by 100 percent inspection. In addition, process control test laminates accompanied each autoclave and oven cycle. Short-beam-shear and flexure test specimens were made from these laminates to verify quality of the processed parts. Inspectors monitored such items as protection of cleaned and/or primed metal details, use of clean cotton gloves, tool surface preparation/contamination, material selection, ply orientation, bagging procedures, and environmental control of work area.

Expandable mylar templates were used during ply layups. Patterns were positioned on the material to control orientation and minimize trimming. Each ply was trimmed and assembled in a layup tool. Mylar patterns were removed and retained for inspection. Number of plies in the laminate was verified by counting the mylar patterns. This also ensured that all separator materials had been removed.

Nondestructive inspections were performed on detail parts using ultrasonic, visual, X-ray, and dimensional inspections. The most widely used inspection process was ultrasonic immersion. The advantage of immersion testing was its adaptability to automatic scanning and recording. It also permitted easier scanning of irregularly shaped test materials and provided good near-surface resolution.

Final assembly inspection was divided into two categories, in-process inspection and final inspection. In-process inspection included fastener holes and fasteners, dimensional tolerance or fit, nondestructive inspection of laminates and joints and sequence checking. Final inspection included borescope, shakedown, and ultrasonic pulse-echo.

Defects

Types of Defects

Defects of various types occurred at all stages of manufacture. The term "defect" as used herein refers to all situations which were contrary to, or different from those defined in materials and processing specifications or engineering design drawings. The defects occurring in this program were categorized by stage of manufacture. A listing of all defects and a brief definition of each follows:

- (1) Defects detected ultrasonically. Attenuation losses in composites result from two separate mechanisms; dissipative hysteresis losses and scattering losses. The former is sensitive to matrix properties, such as degree of cure, modulus and extent of plasticization. Scattering is related to the number and size of the discrete discontinuities within the composite; hence, scattering losses are sensitive to matrix micro-cracking, fiber content and fiber size. An example of a defect detected ultrasonically in a reference standard is shown in Figure 3.
- (2) Rejected process control test panels. As discussed previously, detail parts were accompanied by "witness" test panels. Occasionally, these panels contained defects that were not representative of the corresponding detail part.
- (3) Delamination/Disbond. Separation of adjacent composite/epoxy laminates or separation at adhesive bondlines.

FIGURE 3 DEFECTS DETECTED ULTRASONICALLY

- (4) Dimensional errors. These include thickness out of tolerance, angles out of tolerance or other part dimensions out of tolerance.
- (5) Mislocated detail. Detail parts not properly positioned in the assembly during layup or parts that moved during the curing operation.
- (6) Voids/Porosity. Small air pockets in the epoxy matrix or adhesive bondline.
- (7) Improper cure. Resin rich - localized area into which excessive resin has flowed. Resin starved - an area out of which resin has flowed leaving an insufficient amount of matrix material to properly support the fiber. Resin flow into honeycomb core.
- (8) Warped part. Distorted parts that did not conform to the required shape or parts that contained wavy or crooked fibers.
- (9) Processing errors. Improper processing sequence, unacceptable tooling, process variables not recorded.
- (10) False cut. Inadvertent cuts or gouges caused by improper sawing, grinding or trimming.
- (11) Test failure. Failure of the process control test panel to meet minimum acceptable mechanical properties.
- (12) Hole defects. This category includes elongated holes, splintered holes, oversize holes, mislocated holes, misdrilled pilot holes and overly deep countersinks. An example of a badly splintered hole purposely induced in a test specimen is shown in Figure 4.
- (13) Attachment errors. This includes use of incorrect fasteners and cases where attachments pulled through laminates.
- (14) Material rejections. Includes missing peel ply and omitted adhesive primer. Also includes out of date material and broken screen wire (lightning strike protection).

FIGURE 4 HOLE DEFECT (SPLINTERING)

Frequency of Occurrence

Rejection frequency is presented in terms of various stages of manufacture. The rejection rate associated with process control test panels ("witness" tests) is shown in Table I. These rejections are due to failure of the specimen to meet minimum acceptable values (item 11 above). They are not rejections associated with the quality of the specimen as defined in item 2 above.

Table I Process Verification Testing

Specimen Type	No.	Rejections	Reason	Percentage
Flatwise Tensile	50	13	Low Values	26.0%
Solid Laminate	114	5	Low Values	4.4%
Hybrid	22	1	Low Values	4.5%
Lap Shears	76	6	Low Values	7.9%
	<u>262</u>	<u>25</u>		<u>9.5%</u>

Flatwise tensile tests were conducted using circular specimens with composite faces on aluminum honeycomb core. Low values were obtained when lack of adhesive filleting allowed the faces to pull away from the core. The solid laminate and hybrid categories mentioned in Table I were standard short-beam-shear and flexure specimens. The predominate rejection in those two categories was for low short-beam-shear values. Lap shear tests were conducted using various combinations of composite-to-metal and composite-to-composite adherends with the appropriate adhesive. Various combinations of failures were obtained. A total of 86 autoclave runs, 21 press runs, and 49 oven runs were made for the eight wings from which these specimens were taken. Thus the 25 rejections represent 16% of the processing cycles.

Rejections associated with detail part fabrication are shown in Table II.

The most common type of defect was that detected ultrasonically. Reference standards were fabricated in order to establish a better definition of data obtained in the ultrasonic inspections. Nineteen reference standards were fabricated which were representative of part configuration as well as representative of the typical ultrasonic properties of the part for which it was a reference. It was also necessary for the reference standard to contain both a normal "good bond" condition and a "bad bond" condition representing the defects to be detected in the part.

Final assembly rejections are shown in Table III. Hole defects accounted for 64.6% of all rejections during final assembly. The majority of these were either elongated or splintered holes. Hole splintering was usually a result of inadequate back face support. Improper drill sharpening accounted for most of the elongated holes.

Totals of each wing for detail part fabrication and final assembly are shown in Table IV.

Table II Detail Fabrication Rejection

Defect Description	No.	% of Total Rejections	Ship No.							
			5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Defects detected ultrasonically	37	34.9	4	5	3	5	5	6	4	5
Rejected process control test panels	10	9.4	1		2	1		2	2	2
Delamination	10	9.4		3		2	2	1	1	1
Dimensional	20	18.9	5	2	1	1	3	4	2	2
Mislocated detail	12	11.3	2	1	3	2	1	1	1	1
Void/Porosity	3	2.8	1	1	1					
Improper cure	3	2.8						1	1	1
Warpage	3	2.8					1	2		
Processing errors	7	6.6	1	1	2	1			1	1
False cut	1	.9				1				
	<u>106</u>	<u>99.8</u>	<u>14</u>	<u>13</u>	<u>12</u>	<u>13</u>	<u>12</u>	<u>17</u>	<u>12</u>	<u>13</u>

Table III Final Assembly Rejection

Defect Description	No.	% of Total Rejections	Ship No.							
			5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Hole Defects										
(a) Elongated Hole	39	29.3	9	2	2	2	10	4	1	9
(b) Splintered Hole	16	12.0	6	3	3	1	1			2
(c) Oversize Hole	11	8.3	2		3	4		1	1	
(d) Mislocated Hole	9	6.8	7					1		1
(e) Misdrilled Pilot Hole	8	6.0	4	1		1		1		1
(f) Deep Countersink	3	2.2	1	2						
Trimming Error/False Cut	10	7.5	5	1	3			1		
Bond Line Void/Gap	10	7.5	3	4			1		2	
Attachment Errors										
(a) Incorrect Fastener	5	3.8	3	2						
(b) Pulled-thru fastener	1	.8	1							
Material Rejections										
(a) Missing Peel Ply	8	6.0	8							
(b) Adhesive Primer Missing	3	2.2	1	1	1					
(c) Broken screen wire	2	1.5	2							
(d) Out of date adhesive	1	.8						1		
Contour	3	2.2	3							
Delamination	3	2.2			2	1				
Mislocated Detail	1	.8				1				
	<u>133</u>	<u>99.9</u>	<u>55</u>	<u>16</u>	<u>14</u>	<u>10</u>	<u>12</u>	<u>9</u>	<u>4</u>	<u>13</u>

Table IV Total Defects in Each Wing

Operation	Wing No.							
	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Detail Part	14	13	12	13	12	17	12	13
Final Assembly	<u>55</u>	<u>16</u>	<u>14</u>	<u>10</u>	<u>12</u>	<u>9</u>	<u>4</u>	<u>13</u>
TOTAL	69	29	26	23	24	26	16	26
Rejection Rate Based on No. of Parts*	27.4	11.5	10.3	9.1	9.5	10.3	6.3	10.3

* 252 parts per wing

Rejection summary:

Total Parts = 2016
 Rejections = 239
 % Rejected = 11.8%

Defect Disposition Procedure

Assessment of Criticality

Basic stress analysis of the composite outer wing was performed using NASTRAN finite element analysis techniques. This analysis aided in selection of critical areas to be verified by element tests. Element (verification) test specimens of all critical areas were made during Phase I of the program. Strain gages were placed on key areas of these specimens in order to relate test loads in specimens to test loads on the associated area in the full scale components. "Free field" strain capacity of the critical areas in the wing could thus be determined accurately from these gage readings. Defects that occurred during specimen manufacture were noted. The influence that these defects had or did not have on test results were also noted. Thus, some experience was gained on the effects of the presence of defects in composite material specimens for both static and fatigue testing.

As the static test articles (Wings 1 and 3) were being produced, the acceptance criteria were allowed to be fairly liberal. Defects were "bought off" on detail parts and allowed to be used "for static test only." This was to gain experience with defects in full scale component testing. Defects that could obviously cause premature catastrophic failure were not allowed in the component. Defects that were not so detrimental and defects that had occurred in element tests were allowed in full scale component static tests. Full scale component static and fatigue tests thus added to the overall experience with effect of defects.

Accept reject criteria on production articles were more stringent than on any of the parts produced previously. The purpose was to ensure that all in-service components would be as good or better in quality as the components used for testing. Some discrepancies occurred which had not been previously encountered. Usually the frequency decreased as the experience base increased. For the "unusual" defect, disposition depended on type of defect, criticality of location, assessment of defect severity, and previous experience with the particular type of defect under consideration.

Occasionally defects occurred which were judged to be potentially hazardous to flight safety and durability for which there was no applicable repair. In these instances tests were performed to determine the effects of those defects. A brief list of these tests and conclusions follows:

- (1) Splintered holes in laminates loaded in tension - Hole quality apparently had very little effect on the tensile strength of laminates.
- (2) Environmental effects - Big loss in strength with moisture and elevated temperature in the matrix dominated properties.
- (3) Testing of expired material - Most material was requalified for use after normal shelf life was exceeded.
- (4) Contamination of titanium surfaces - Bond strength to Titanium is very sensitive to surface preparation.
- (5) Cleaning methods for surfaces of composite laminates exposed to handling - Normal procedure is to leave a peel ply on surface until just prior to bonding operation. Sometimes parts were stripped of their peel ply prematurely with resulting contamination. Light sanding and wiping with methylethyl ketone (MEK) proved to be an acceptable method for cleaning contaminated surfaces.
- (6) Strength/durability tests on laminates with excessive porosity - Tensile tests showed laminates with holes were slightly weaker with porosity than the unflawed laminates. In fatigue tests there was no detectable difference.
- (7) Effect of ply stacking on strength of core bond to skin - Found to have very little effect for the configurations chosen. Use of a hybrid laminate containing boron and graphite/epoxy plies did make a considerable improvement in performance of core bond strength when compared to all graphite/epoxy.

When a defect occurred in a part or assembly, there were three choices available for disposition: accept, replace, or repair. Many standard repair procedures, similar to those used in metallic structure were found to be appropriate in the composite outer wing. Oversize holes were bushed to provide proper fastener hole diameter, oversize or "salvage" fasteners were used, occasionally holes were repaired using an epoxy paste adhesive. Other repairs included the injection of an adhesive through small holes to fill a void or delamination, addition of doublers or reinforcing plies, and removal and replacement of material.

Defect Record

Since defects were located and defined by several different methods, final detail inspection of large cover assemblies was greatly aided by implementation of full scale mylar templates showing the trimmed outline of the part and location of all visible doublers, shims, cutouts, and holes, and some internal details. During ultrasonic, visual, X-ray, and dimensional inspection defects were entered on a "working mylar" as shown in Figure 5. The working mylar was made from a master. The mylar was then used to record specific areas where additional testing and/or repair was to be accomplished. A repair mylar was then made for shop use in accomplishing the repair. This aided location of repair on the component.

Scrapped Parts

Eleven detail parts out of a total of 2016 were scrapped. There were no scrapped parts during final assembly - all occurred during detail part manufacture. The eleven that were scrapped represent 0.5% of the total parts required.

Disposition by Component

Figure 6 illustrates the disposition of all defects occurring during detail part fabrication. Of the 106 rejections, 11 resulted in scrapped parts (10.4%) and there were 47 repairs required (44.3% of the rejections). Forty-eight rejections (45.3%) were accepted with no further action taken.

Disposition of defects occurring in final assembly is shown in Figure 7. There were 133 total rejections. No parts were scrapped, 113 defects (85%) required corrective action and 20 defects (15%) were accepted with no further correction required.

Summary and Conclusions

Flaws and defects occurring in composite structure are not a prohibitive influence on production. Accept/reject criteria in this program were not sufficiently developed to allow flaws or defects without rejecting the part. Consequently, the rejection rate was higher than should be expected with well developed accept/reject criteria. In spite of this, the overall rate based on total part count was only 11.8%.

In general the defects were handled by simple repairs. Only 0.5% of the parts were scrapped.

The most common flaws in detail part fabrication were those detected by ultrasonic inspection. Hole defects accounted for two-thirds of the defects experienced in final assembly.

FIGURE 5 FULL SIZE MYLAR USED TO RECORD AND LOCATE DEFECTS

FIGURE 6 DISPOSITION OF REJECTIONS - DETAIL PART FABRICATION

FIGURE 7 DISPOSITION OF REJECTIONS - FINAL ASSEMBLY

References

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